

An educational program proposition on the basis of cooperative and applied methods by orienting peers to reinforce some of their technical basketball skills for the first year secondary school.

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Abstract

The aim from this study is to know the influence of using cooperative and orienting peers learning (reciprocal) methods in learning some basketball skills for the first year secondary school. The experimental method has been used on a sample of (40) students, that have been randomly chosen, and divided into two experimental equal groups with a number of (20) students. The cooperative learning was used with the first one and the peers learning with the second one, and to collect datas , a two methods teaching program was used , by precisising the performance tests. After datas collection and its analysis statistically using the statistic packets SPSS , the results have shown the importance of using a developed strategy like cooperative method learning (learning together) and peers learning , in which the teaching process passes from the teacher to the learner , then the students becomes the center of this operation , in addition to giving much importance to the physical , psychologic , learner performance .

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I. -Introduction:

In the modern times, we are witnessing a qualitative jump in all scientific and disciplines, many scientists have contributed in this development in all knowledge fields. We consider sports science as one of the important domains that have witnessed a great change among sciences that participated in the qualitative movement in all physical sports. scientists have also developed new methods that are adapted with the new progress that is happening in knowledge fields (Al Hila ,2003, P90) This has been positively reflected in the educational systems, with different countries currently paying increasing attention to the quality of learning and the quality of learning outcomes, and the basics are one of the main pillars of the process of effective education in the field of physical and sports education, In fact, effective training is not just an ordinary man's job , but is a process designed by a multifaceted project with known boundaries and anchors, directly related to the specificities of that group under training , and therefore the Understanding of these specifics and factors affecting the process of study are among the basic rules that workers in this field of study must know, and understanding the various paragraphs for which decisions are made to build the basic rules of study (Nahed, 1989, p17)

(Singer, 1995, p62) believes that it is necessary for the teacher to have multiple teaching technique choices, so that he does not depend on one particular style, since the use of a unified method for all learners may not lead to healthy learning. The success of the learning process and upgrading the level of learning must be complemented by the efforts of the students and their method, this is why the researchers who rely on modern learning methods see that the involvement of the learner in the learning process has many positive aspects because he is the center of the learning process and part of it. Collaborative and peer-to-peer learning methods are considered to be the theoreticians advocated ways and sports professionals. Because of its importance in making the learner part of the learning process, where the researcher believes that they fit with his study and the sample of his research because of the positive benefits of these methods when used by previous researchers in other studies, including the study of (Abdul Zahra, 2013) (Abdul Aziz, 2015), (Al Diwan, 2016) Since the method of collaborative learning aims to improve and activate the ideas of learners who work in groups, teach each other and talk to each other, so that all members of the group feel the responsibility of the group direction, in addition to that , the use of this method leads to the development of team spirit among learners and the development of social skills (Hemo, 2010, p32) and this was

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confirmed by the Study of (Zaytouni, 2011), As for the peer method, it is one of the teaching methods that leads to the effective participation of the learner, going beyond indoctrination to actively contribute to the implementation of some parts of the physical education lesson through the exchange of roles with the teacher and the learners in our time and among the learners (Khafaka & Sayh, 2008, p89), and this is what we can notice in the study of (Ali, 2012), And through the research team's follow-up to research and studies and their experience in the field of teaching methods, and as a former professor for the secondary level, he noticed the low skill level of the pupils as they face several difficulties in learning skills, and that the performance is not adequate to the required level, especially the skills (shooting from the jump and The chest passing) due to its difficulty and its interconnectivity with each other in ending the attack the lack of time dedicated to physical sports to promote the students level to reach the right performance , also the increasing number of students in the class ,all of this has decreased the rythm of learning process ,and the developement of the basketball skills, the researcher has noticed the nonexistence of a clear strategy for the educational activity based on individual differences , because the classic methods give uncertain results of success , we can see that one learner could obtain good grades in the same time other learner could obtain low grades due to their ability and acceptance to some specific skills .that is why all learners are experienced in the same unit, the same repetitions , the same resting time , which takes to the differenciaton in the learning and performance ability. This is supported by (Zaghloul & Hani, 2001, P84) in their opinion about changing the classic imposed way of teaching (Verbal explanation) to reach the aims and modern objects of education , and the importance of its adaptation to the physical and psychologic growth, to fulfill the needs of learners . The researcher insists on that by insisting on the importance of new technologies on education environement. (Zaghloul & Hani, 2001, P84) Therefore, the idea was to use the two styles of cooperative education and peer education because of their outstanding importance in raising the competence of learners and providing educational opportunities for students better than the previously approved methods (regular teaching) and on this basis we ask the following question: Does the use of cooperative learning and peer learning have a positive effect on improving the technical performance of some basketball skills among first secondary students?

II. Method:

1-2- Research Society and Sample:

The research sample was deliberately chosen from 204 students in the first year of secondary school for the academic year 2018/2019, and (10) students were randomly selected to conduct an exploratory experiment on them. The research sample was chosen randomly and by lottery, the total number of the basic sample was 40 students, and they were divided into two groups equally (20) students for each group, the first experimental studied by the cooperative learning method and the second experimental by the peer method

2-2- Research Procedures:

2-2-1- Research method: The researcher used the experimental method with two equal groups in order to suit it to solve the research problem because 'the most important characteristic of accurate scientific activity is the use of experiment method' (Mahjoub, 1983, p330)

2-2-2- Defining the variables and how to measure them:

The variables of this study are the two styles of cooperative learning and peer learning as two main variables that are programmed in an educational program, and the technical performance of basketball skills as a dependent variable that will be measured by the skill tests under study.

2-2-3- The sample homogeneity and the equivalence of the two research groups:

The homogeneity of the sample: the moderation of the individuals basic research sample distribution was confirmed in the growth, physical and skill variables (under study) As shown in Table (01).

Moderation of the research sample distribution in the growth, physical and skill variables.

variables		Measurement unit	average rate	Standard deviation	Twisting coefficient	Levene test		F max hartleys
						t	sig	
Growth variables	age	year	16.92	1.11	0.33	0.61	0.960	1.382
	length	cm	175.09	3.22	0.68	0.59	0.579	2.427
	weight	kg	61.21	3.73	0.93	0.87	0.631	0.984
Physical variables	Homogeneity between eyes and hands	kg	22.75	0.46	0.74	0.68	0.587	0.635
	Vertical jump from stability	nbr	13.02	1.77	0.89	0.663	0.740	0.899
	Sprint(22) in a curve	cm	5.77	1.09	0.93	0.738	0.574	0.787
	Zigzag run	second	25.90	1.48	0.67	0.768	0.637	0.924
Skill level	Shoot from jump	sec	14.85	5.56	0.68	0.636	0.573	0.987
	Chest pass	degree	22.68	3.41	0.75	0.728	0.632	0.875

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It is evident from Table (1) that the curve coefficients are situated between (- + 3), indicating that the sample represents a homogeneous moderate population in the previous variables. We also note from the above table also that the sig values (significance) of the t- Levene test is all greater than 5% and from that we accept the zero hypothesis, with no differences in variance between the two groups. And given a table of **F. Max Hartley**, the calculated p-max values appear to be less than the tabular value of 2.86, thus accepting the null hypothesis in the sense of the two samples homogeneity in the variables under study.

Sample Equivalence: The researcher conducted parity between the experimental and control groups in the previous variables that may affect the results of the study, by calculating the significance of the differences between the two groups. Table No. (2) illustrates this.

Table No. 02 shows the equivalence of the sample in the research variables

variables		Measurement unit	Collaborative learning method		Peer to peer learning style		Calculated T
			M	X	M	X	
Growth variables	age	year	16.33	0.65	16.69	0.78	0.69
	length	cm	1.75	1.47	1.74	1.38	1.16
	weight	kg	61.07	4.35	61.40	4.67	0.53
Physical variables	Homogeneity between eyes and hands	kg	22.97	0.39	22.56	0.41	1.36
	Vertical jump from stability	nbr	13.02	1.54	13.45	1.89	0.183
	Sprint(22) in a curve	cm	5.98	0.82	5.66	0.71	0.740
	Zigzag run in barrow way	second	25.91	1.85	25.68	1.47	0.340
Skill level	Shoot from jump	sec	14.37	4.56	14.68	4.77	0.638
	Chest pass	degree	22.21	5.36	22.59	5.58	0.934

Table value (t) at (0.05) level = 2.02, degree of freedom (38)

It is evident through (02) that there are no statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups, as the calculated value of 'T' was less than the tabular value of 'T' (2.02), indicating parity of the two study groups.

2-2-4- Research Tools:

- **The forms:** there were many between the questionnaire for the expert opinion on the validity and suitability of tools and devices, the standard paper (duty) and the form for recording data for pre-experiment measurements, measurements of tools scientific coefficient (psychometric properties) or post-trial measurements.

Physical and skill tests:

First: Physical exams: (Darwish & Al-Hamahmi, 2002, p172)

Throwing basketball on the wall test for (30) seconds

Throwing a handball weighing 800 g to the maximum distance to measure the characteristic force of the arm's speed

- The vertical jump from stability to measure the force characteristic of the speed of the two legs

Sprint (20) m in a curve to measure the speed transition (Marzouq, 2001, p228)

Slalom running with the Barrow agility method (Darwish, 2002, p195)

Skill tests: * The jump correction test to measure the skill accuracy of the correction

* The chest scroll test to measure its accuracy (Marzouq, 2001, p209)

2-2-5- Scientific parameters of the selected test (under study):

Test validation:

Logical validation: by finding the square root of the reliability coefficient of the test. Table No. (4) shows that the test has high logical validity.

Distinguishing validation: To verify the validity of the tests, the researcher tended to use the validity of differentiation by applying the tests on two groups, one of which (10) students were not distinguished and the second group (10) distinguished from those who represented the institution's basketball team for the academic year 2018-2019 and were excluded from the research Main experience

The differences indication between the two Non distinct and distinct groups in the research variables:

variables		Measurement unit	The non-distinguished group		Distinguished group		T value	Kind of significance
			s	z	s	z		
Physical variables	Homogeneity between eyes and hands	kg	23.22	0.87	28.71	0.57	4.93	moral
	Vertical jump from stability	nbr	13.21	1.24	24.80	3.06	9.69	moral
	Sprint(22) in a curve	cm	5.45	0.71	4.01	0.98	3.68	moral
	Zigzag run in barrow way	second	26.07	1.84	22.11	0.91	5.09	moral
Skill level	Shoot from jump	sec	14.23	4.36	63.31	7.84	32.2	moral
	Chest pass	degree	23.05	5.11	66.248	5.269	38.1	moral

Table (t) value at (0.05) = (2.10)

Table (03) shows that there are statistically significant differences in favor of the distinct group in the skill performance of the skills under research, which indicates the validity of the tests in measuring what they were designed for.

Tests Stability: The researchers applied the tests and then re-applied them on the members of the exploratory research sample with a time difference of

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(8) days. The values of the coefficient reliability of the tests under research came respectively (0.91, 0.93), which indicates that the tests have high stability coefficients. The correlation coefficient between the first and second application of physical and skill performance tests (D) was found for the unmarked group (6 tested), which is shown in Table 04

Correlation coefficient between the first and second applications in research variables n 1 = 10

variables		Measurement unit	First application		Second application		Correlation coeffic	Reliability coeffic
			s	z	s	z		
Physical variables	Homogeneity between eyes and hands	degree	23.22	0.87	23.29	0.91	*0.859	0.92
	Vertical jump from stability	cm	13.21	1.24	13.23	1.32	*0.916	0.95
	Sprint(22) in a curve	second	5.45	0.71	5.41	0.65	*0.967	0.98
	Zigzag run in barrow way	second	26.07	1.84	26.20	1.92	*0.793	0.89
Skill	Shoot from jump	degree	14.23	4.36	14.31	4.48	*0.832	0.91
	Chest pass	degree	23.05	5.11	23.28	2.39	*0.864	0.92

R value at 0.05 = 0.756 level

Where $n = 10$ / c -value at 0.05 = 1.812 where $n = 10$

It is evident from Table No. (04) that there is a statistically significant correlation at a level of significance 0.05 between the first and second application in the selected physical and skill tests, and at the same time the high (subjective) statistical validity of those tests, as it indicates that there are no statistically significant differences between the two applications, because The value of the self-validation factor is less than the tabular 'T' value, which also confirms the validity of the test

2-2-6- Field Test Procedures:

The general framework of the educational program: The vocabulary of the educational units was developed based on the original specialized references and some studies as , study (Hassanein, 1995), (Allawi & Radwan, 1994) (Hamdan, 2011), and the study of (Min W, 2012), (Abu Bakr, 2014), (Raouf, 2012), (Kaya & Baris, 2011), and the study of (Ahmad, 2017). After asking advice from a number of specialists in the field of teaching and training and other qualified researchers in the field of teaching, and based on that , the content of the educational units was modified to reach its final form (8) educational units to learn the two correction skills of stability and the chest pass with basketball

- The educational program: An educational program was developed for the two experimental groups for the shooting skills from stability and the basketball chest pass using the cooperative learning method and the peer method, over a period of eight (8) weeks, which is the period that it took to

apply the educational program for the two skills. Collaborative learning method group. The time is divided as follows: Total time (60) d (10) minutes of general warm-up for all parts of the body and then a special warm-up for the ball (7) minutes in which the skill is explained and presented by the lecturer (teacher) with the help of applied models from one or more students. The practical part takes (35) minutes to be applied by defining a set of exercises, the skill composed of the two applied skills by students through a form (standard paper). And a time of (08) minutes of recovery exercises, returning to normal, greeting and leaving, then changing clothes

Peer style group: The same division of the previous time in terms of preparation and warm-up exercises, but the difference is in the main part through the following: The separation is organized in pairs and each individual is assigned to do a special role, so that one of them performs and the other observes and the role of the performer is to complete the work and make decisions. It is noticed that the feedback is given to the performer, and he contacts the teacher.

2-2-7- Statistical treatment:

The following appropriate statistical methods were adopted: - the percentage - the arithmetic mean - the standard deviation - the mode - the curve coefficient - the **Levene test** - **Hartley's Great F max** test - Simple correlation coefficient (Pearson) - T-test for symmetric and asymmetric samples - Improvement ratios.

III. Results:

The results are presented, analyzed and discussed in light of the research hypotheses as follows:

Presentation and analysis of the results:

1- Presentation of the significance of the differences between the pre and post measurements of the first experimental group in the variables under study.

The arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and (t) value and its significance between the pre and post measurement averages of the peer-method group of the two skills under study

variables	Measurement test	Pre test		Post test		Average difference	calculated) T
		(1)m	(1)s	(2)m	(2)s		
From jump shooting	degree	14.68	4.77	36.23	6.87	32.421	14.68
Chest pass	degree	22.59	5.58	49.47	3.25	29.63	26.88

Table (05) shows that the calculated (t) values were greater than its tabular value of (2.86) at the level of significance (0.05) and below the degree of freedom (19), which indicates the existence of significant differences

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between the pre and post-tests of the experimental group in the tests of basketball skills. The study is for the benefit of the post tests. The calculated (t) values were a function and greater than the tabular in the post measurements of the first experimental group in the skill variables.

2- Presentation of the differences significance between the pre and post measurements of the second experimental group in the variables under study.

The arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and (t) value and its significance between the pre and post measurement averages of the cooperative learning method group of the two skills under study.

variables	Measurement test	Post test		Pre test		Average difference	calculated) T
		(1)m	(1)s	(2)m	(2)s		
From jump shooting	degree	14.37	4.56	58.76	8.63	40.56	14.37
Chest pass	degree	22.21	5.36	63.85	4.42	37.84	41.64

Table (06) shows that the calculated (t) values were greater than the tabular value of (2.86) at the level of significance (0.05) and below the degree of freedom (19), which indicates the existence of significant differences between the pre and post-tests of the experimental group in the two tests of basketball skills. The study is in favor of the dimensional tests, as the calculated (t) values were a function and greater than the tabular in the post measurements of the second experimental skill variables group.

3- Displaying the significance of the differences between the post measurements of the two experimental groups in the variables under study.

The arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and (t) value and its significance between the two post averages of the experimental and control groups in search variables

variables	Peer method		Improvement percent %	Cooperative method		Improvement percent %	T value	Difference between averages
	s	z		s	z			
Shooting from jump	36.23	6.87	146.79	58.76	8.63	308.9	10.86	22.56
Chest pass	49.47	3.25	118.99	63.85	4.42	187.4	12.72	14.38

Table (07) shows that the calculated value of (t) was greater than its tabular value of (2.02) at a level of significance (0.05) and under a degree of freedom (38), which indicates the existence of significant differences between the two groups in the skills of correction and passing accuracy in favor of the cooperative learning method group. The two rates of improvement for the cooperative learning style group were (308.90% - 187.48%), which is higher than the two improvement rates for the peer style group, which was estimated (146.79% - 118.99%).

IV. Discussion:

It's clear through the results in table number (05) the existence of a prior difference for the post measurement of peer group method ,The research team attributes the reason for these differences significance to the use of the application method under peer guidance, which facilitated the process of understanding, comprehension and awareness of the skill, through a clear graduation in the presentation of the two preparation skills in its three sections (preparatory, basic, final), as the reciprocal method is considered one of the modern methods that lead when applied to a new form of relationships between the teacher and the learner that contributes to the development of interdependence and social relations, (Ahmed, 2006, p109) says "The reciprocal method is considered as a new method, with a reality and a method that require a new nature of the circle , social and psychological requirements for both the teacher and the learner, where Major modifications and changes must be made in the commanding behavior that leads to the perception of a new situation that may occur in the class. "The researcher believes that the system of reciprocal work between the two competing students creates an atmosphere of fun and excitement and a kind of self-challenge and a challenge to the student's ability and in this confirms (Nahda & Zaid, 2001, p85) Competition contributes to an abundant share in developing the capabilities of the individual and developing their skills, and one of the conditions for the success of teaching the basic principles of the skill is that its education happens in the form of the competition. (Mohsen, 2006), (Munther, 2007), (Abdel Aziz, 2015), (Al-Diwan, 2016) study. These studies confirm that the reciprocal method led to an improvement in the level of skill performance, and this is confirmed by the results of the current study Whereas, the reciprocal method had a positive effect on improving the technical performance of the skills under study.

Its noticeable through table number (06) the existence of differences between the two measurements (prior and post) for the post measurement of cooperative method group .The research team attributes the reasons for this difference to the effectiveness of the collaborative (integrative) method in terms of planning and organizing the educational unit and how to apply the three skill sections (preparatory, main and final) to be learned in the educational unit, which makes it easier for the learners to acquire the researched skill. Also, the educational situations that the learners were exposed to, which clearly characterizes the educational goal, and this was

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not known in the educational units followed in previous teaching. This is confirmed by Fouad Salman Qilada 'that the clarity of goals and their definition in light of specific behavior or levels of performance because they are meaningful and effective (**Qilada, 1989, p177**) The research team also believes that cooperative learning is consistent with the students' tendencies and desires to participate and cooperate in addition to that , dividing students into heterogeneous groups increases participation within the group to achieve a common goal and thus make them more realistic and active towards learning and knowing what is New, as cooperative learning develops positive interdependence among group members by exchanging information and ideas during the practical application of the skill with group members, discussing among them, ensuring correct opinions of the skill and clarifying it to others, encouraging each other and addressing information openly, clearly among the members, and ensuring that they understand the skill or benefit Of the proposals and opinions of all members of the group and the mutual contact between them, and in this regard Hassan Zaitoun (2003) mentions' that the integration of group members in performance and teamwork helps on the success of the team and works on the success of the whole group in achieving the desired goals' (**Zaitoun, 2003, p98**), and these results are consistent with the conclusions of some previous studies and research linked to the study of (**Hemo, 2010**), (**Salem, 2013**), (**Abdel Aziz, 2015**), (**al-Diwan, 2016**) Which confirms the effectiveness of the cooperative learning method through the results of their studies in favor of post measurements.

The results of the table showed that there are statistically significant differences in favor of the experimental group in the skill level when comparing the two post measurements experimental groups, where the experimental group by the cooperative learning method was superior to the peer method group in the level of skill performance of the two skills under study. The research team attributes the reason for the differences to the nature of the cooperative learning method, which provided an opportunity for the learner to shift from negativity in learning to positivity in learning and his role to receive everything thrown at him and apply all the teacher's orders. The decisions about the application phase are transferred from the teacher to the student, and what this method allows From developing pupils' abilities to solve educational problems, increasing their creativity and applying the skill in many different situations, while minimizing the different points of view with colleagues, giving a safe opportunity to try ,

commit mistakes and learn from these mistakes after their recurrence, as this method also allowed them to work in a team spirit and practice. Each student has a role assigned to him within the educational group research that students communicate with each other and discuss the course material and help each other in learning it by exchanging their role with others to reach in the end the matter to a common collective goal that the group as a whole seeks, which led to the attention of each member in The group to his colleagues and the application of the instructions he receives, using worksheets and performance standards designed by the teacher and the educational , technical instructions , legal , explanatory, and the volume of work, whether it is in frequency, time, number, or groups, and cognitive information about the skill to be learned. To be achieved. In this matter states Johnson David (1999) However, learning within small groups of students allows them to work effectively and help each other to raise the level of each other and achieve the learning goal (**David, 1999, p215**). This result is consistent with the results of the study of (**Kaya, 2013**), the study of (**al-Sharif, 2013**) and the study of (**Salem, 2013**), the study of (**Abdel Aziz, 2015**), the study of (**Al Diwan, 2016**), as these studies indicated the superiority of cooperative education over the reciprocal method or the traditional method in all the variables that dealt with their studies, due to the excitement, cooperation, motivation, and progressive and final achievement of cooperative education. This fulfills the third assumption.

V. Conclusion:

In light of the researchers' interest, it seems an urgent need to employ various contemporary teaching strategies that work on acquiring students methods of analysis and synthesis and developing their skills, especially mobility, so it was necessary to use an advanced strategy such as cooperative learning and peer learning in which the educational process is transferred from the teacher to the learner and the student becomes The center of this process, and the teacher's role in it is to direct, guide and organize, as well as pay attention to the physical, psychological and skill aspects of the learners, and in light of the results of the study we conducted, we concluded that teaching using the method of cooperative learning and peer learning has a positive effect on improving the basketball correction and passing technical performance skills with Excellence of cooperative learning group. In light of the conclusions and results of the study, we recommend the adoption of cooperative learning and peer learning in

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teaching the two skills of correction from the jump and the chest pass among first-year secondary school students. Conducting further studies to identify the effect of using cooperative learning and peer learning on the physical, emotional and impressive side. With other similar studies conducted at different age, educational and academic stages that were not covered by the current study.

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